

Sustainable digitalization survey – Part 2

Dear participants,

As part of the Research Pilot 3 of the InNoWest project, we are exploring the possibilities of how the consumption of digital devices and services could be made sustainable.

A few **important terms** first:

- **Fair production conditions**
Wages and working hours that correspond to the commitment and effort of the employees; fairly equipped workplaces or working environments; compliance with labor law regulations in the respective country for the manufacturing of corresponding products, such as technical devices, and services, such as content moderation or programming jobs
- **Environmentally friendly**
(in the context of using social media, surfing on the internet, browsing websites): Minimalistic handling or minimalist use of multimedia content (videos, images, emojis and filter functions in social media, etc.) → Using or viewing this content requires electricity, which causes CO2 emissions.
- **Streaming**
Real-time transmission of data, i.e. the data can be viewed or listened to during transmission
- **Social Media**
Social media encompasses social platforms of all kinds, such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, Snapchat, Reddit, LinkedIn, X, Twitch, Pinterest, etc.

You can find more information on the topic of **sustainable digitalization** here:

http://www.t1p.de/innowest_rp3

General information

1. **Please enter your individual PIN, which you have received from us, here:**

2. Your gender:

- male
- female
- diverse
- No answer

3. Your age

- under 15 years old
- 15-17 years old
- 18-20 years old
- 21-23 years old
- 24-26 years old
- More than 26 years old
- No answer

4. I am aware that fairly produced products and services cost more.

- Yes
- Partly aware
- No, rather not
- No, not at all

5. I am willing to pay more for fairly produced products and services.

- Yes
- Partly willing
- No, rather not
- No, not at all

6. I am willing to refrain from buying products such as smartphones from companies that are known for their poor treatment of their employees and the environment.

- Yes, definitely
- Yes
- Partly willing
- No, rather not
- No, not at all

- 7. It is important to me to read content on websites that support the text with appealing multimedia content (such as music, videos, audio, images).**
- Yes
 - Rather yes
 - Rather no
 - No
- 8. When I make phone calls on my smartphone, I also switch on the video.**
- Yes
 - Rather yes
 - Rather no
 - No
- 9. When I have enough money and have had my smartphone for a while, I prefer to buy the newest model.**
- Yes
 - Rather yes
 - Rather no
 - No
- 10. If I received a notification from a media or data processing program that photos or videos could be archived or deleted, I would:**
- Would like to have the media deleted automatically
 - Want to check the media selected for deletion before deletion
 - Ignore the message
 - Other
- 11. I prefer consuming digital content (such as videos, music, films) in streaming mode.**
- Yes
 - No
 - I have no preferences in this regard.
 - I do not consume streaming content.

12. I stream digital content in the highest quality.

- Yes, always
- Yes, most of the time
- No, rather not
- No, never
- I cannot answer this question.

13. I am willing to store my videos locally on my devices to avoid streaming services.

- Yes
- I will think about it.
- I'm not sure.
- No
- I can't answer this question.

14. I am willing to use a cheaper streaming service tariff and having to download my content in return.

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure.

15. I am willing to reduce the quality of the media display (audio or video) in order to reduce the amount of transmitted data.

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure.
- I will think about it.

16. If my smartphone doesn't work or doesn't work properly ...

- I throw it away.
- I dispose it sustainably at an appropriate place.
- I try to repair my smartphone first.
- Other

17. If my smartphone no longer works ...

- I buy a new device.
- I buy a repaired device.
- I buy a second-hand device.
- I wait until I get a used device from a friend.
- Other

18. When I buy a new smartphone, the most important criterion is:

- the price
- the model or brand
- the repairability of the device
- the sustainable production of the device
- the transparency of the information regarding the manufacture of the device
- Other

Please specify "Other"

Your user behaviour in the future?

Below we ask about your willingness to change your user behaviour in the future.

Here are the possible scenarios - please read carefully so that you know what you are actually ticking.

- **Using environmentally friendly websites:** Where possible, use websites with less multimedia content and dynamic elements
- **Phone calls without video:** Refraining from the video option for phone calls.
- **Not buying a new device:** Refraining from the newest model of a smartphone, for example to conserve natural resources such as water and rare earths.
- **Minimizing the amount of data:** e.g. storing photos, videos, etc. locally on the devices or in the cloud
- **Storing locally instead of streaming:** Storing videos on the devices to avoid streaming services.
- **Reducing the quality:** Using media such as video or audio in lower quality to reduce the amount of data transferred
- **Switching off the smartphone overnight:** And doing it completely - with the power off button.
- **Using energy-saving mode** on the devices used.

We will now ask you step by step which of the above-mentioned aspects of user behaviour you are already implementing or would like to implement in the future, which aspects you doubt will have any effect at all and for which aspects you cannot imagine to change your user behaviour in the future. Don't forget: The answers are anonymous, please answer honestly :-).

19. I already do the following things all the time or most of the time:

(maximum three responses)

- Making phone calls without video
- Buying used devices instead of new ones
- Minimizing the amount of data I store; e.g. by taking fewer photos
- Minimizing the amount of data I consume; e.g. by consuming content in a lower quality
- Saving data locally on the device instead of streaming it
- Reducing the playback quality of media content
- Switching off my smartphone overnight
- Using the devices' energy-saving mode

20. I will do the following things in the future:

(maximum three responses)

- Making phone calls without video
- Buying used devices instead of new ones
- Minimizing the amount of data I store; e.g. by taking fewer photos
- Minimizing the amount of data I consume; e.g. by consuming content in a lower quality
- Saving data locally on the device instead of streaming it
- Reducing the playback quality of media content
- Switching off my smartphone overnight
- Using the devices' energy-saving mode

21. I am unsure whether the following aspects have any effect at all:

(maximum three responses)

- Using environmentally friendly websites
- Making phone calls without video
- Buying used devices instead of new ones
- Minimizing the amount of data I store; e.g. by taking fewer photos
- Minimizing the amount of data I consume; e.g. by consuming content in a lower quality
- Saving data locally on the device instead of streaming it
- Reducing the playback quality of media content
- Switching off my smartphone overnight
- Using the devices' energy-saving mode

22. I will at least think about the following changes in my user behavior:

(maximum three responses)

- Using environmentally friendly websites
- Making phone calls without video
- Buying used devices instead of new ones
- Minimizing the amount of data I store; e.g. by taking fewer photos
- Minimizing the amount of data I consume; e.g. by consuming content in a lower quality
- Saving data locally on the device instead of streaming it
- Reducing the playback quality of media content
- Switching off my smartphone overnight
- Using the devices' energy-saving mode

23. I can't even imagine the following changes in my user behavior:

(maximum three responses)

- Using environmentally friendly websites
- Making phone calls without video
- Buying used devices instead of new ones
- Minimizing the amount of data I store; e.g. by taking fewer photos
- Minimizing the amount of data I consume; e.g. by consuming content in a lower quality
- Saving data locally on the device instead of streaming it
- Reducing the playback quality of media content
- Switching off my smartphone overnight
- Using the devices' energy-saving mode

24. I am willing to pay more for a smartphone that was manufactured under sustainable conditions ...

- up to 100% (600 € instead of 300 €)
- between 75% and 100% more (between 525 € and 600 € instead of 300 €)
- between 50% and 75% more (between 450 € and 525 € instead of 300 €)
- between 25% and 50% more (between 375 € and 450 € instead of 300 €)
- between 10% and 25% more (between 330 € and 375 € instead of 300 €)
- up to 10% more (max. 330 € instead of 300 €)
- I can't afford to pay more.
- I am not willing to pay more.

Thank you for your participation!